

MODULES OF 8051

TIMERS, SERIAL COMMUNICATION PORT,
INTERRUPTS

8051 timer/counter

Timers /Counters Programming

- The 8051 has 2 timers/counters: timer/counter 0 and timer/counter 1. They can be used as
 1. The **timer** is used as a time delay generator.
 - The clock source is the **internal** crystal frequency of the 8051.
 2. An event **counter**.
 - **External input** from input pin to count the number of events on registers.
 - These clock pulses count represent the number of people passing through an entrance, or the number of wheel rotations, or any other event that can be converted to pulses.

Timer

- Set the initial value of registers
- Start the timer and then the 8051 counts up.
- Input from internal system clock (machine cycle)
- When the registers equal to 0 and the 8051 sets a bit to denote time out

Counter

- Count the number of events
 - Show the number of events on registers
 - External input from T0 input pin (P3.4) for Counter 0
 - External input from T1 input pin (P3.5) for Counter 1
 - **External input** from Tx input pin.
 - We use Tx to denote T0 or T1.

Registers Used in Timer/Counter

- TH₀, TL₀- For Timer 0
- TH₁, TL₁- For Timer 1
- TMOD (Timer mode register)
- TCON (Timer control register)

Basic Registers of the Timer

- Both timer 0 and timer 1 are 16 bits wide.
 - These registers stores
 - the time delay as a timer
 - the number of events as a counter
 - Timer 0: **TH₀** & **TL₀**
 - Timer 0 high byte, timer 0 low byte
 - Timer 1: **TH₁** & **TL₁**
 - Timer 1 high byte, timer 1 low byte
 - Each 16-bit timer can be accessed as two separate registers of low byte and high byte.

Timer Registers

Timer 0

Timer 1

TMOD Register

- Timer mode register: **TMOD**

MOV TMOD, #21H

- An 8-bit register
- Set the usage mode for two timers
 - Set lower 4 bits for Timer 0 (Set to 0000 if not used)
 - Set upper 4 bits for Timer 1 (Set to 0000 if not used)
- Not bit-addressable

(MSB)

(LSB)

GATE	C/T'	M1	M0	GATE	C/T'	M1	M0
Timer 1				Timer 0			

Figure 9-3. TMOD Register

GATE Gating control when set. Timer/counter is enabled only while the INTx pin is high and the TRx control pin is set. When cleared, the timer is enabled whenever the TRx control bit is set.

C/T' Timer or counter selected cleared for timer operation (input from internal system clock). Set for counter operation (input from Tx input pin).

M1 Mode bit 1

M0 Mode bit 0

(MSB)

(LSB)

GATE	C/T	M1	M0	GATE	C/T	M1	M0
Timer 1				Timer 0			

C/T' (Clock/Timer)

- This bit is used to decide whether the timer is used as a delay generator or an event counter.
- $C/T' = 0$: timer
- $C/T' = 1$: counter

Gate

- Every timer has a mean of starting and stopping.
 - $GATE=0$
 - **Internal** control
 - The start and stop of the timer are controlled by way of **software**.
 - Set/clear the TR for start/stop timer.
 - $GATE=1$
 - **External** control
 - The hardware way of starting and stopping the timer by **software** and **an external source**.
 - Timer/counter is enabled only while the INT pin is high and the TR control pin is set (TR).

M1, M0

- M0 and M1 select the timer mode for timers 0 & 1.

M1	M0	Mode	Operating Mode
0	0	0	13-bit timer mode 8-bit THx + 5-bit TLx (x= 0 or 1)
0	1	1	16-bit timer mode 8-bit THx + 8-bit TLx
1	0	2	8-bit auto reload 8-bit auto reload timer/counter; THx holds a value which is to be reloaded into TLx each time it overflows.
1	1	3	Split timer mode

Example 9-3

Find the value for TMOD if we want to program timer 0 in mode 2, use 8051 XTAL for the clock source, and use instructions to start and stop the timer.

Solution:

timer 1 timer 0

TMOD= 0000 0010

Timer 1 is not used.
Timer 0, **mode 2**,
C/T' = 0 to use XTAL clock source (timer)
gate = 0 to use internal (**software**)
start and stop method.

Timer modes

Mode 0

Mode 1

Mode 2

Mode 3

TCON Register (1/2)

- Timer control register: **TCON**
 - Upper nibble for timer/counter, lower nibble for interrupts
- **TR** (run control bit)
 - TR0 for Timer/counter 0; TR1 for Timer/counter 1.
 - TR is set by programmer to turn timer/counter on/off.
 - TR=0: off (stop)
 - TR=1: on (start)

(MSB)

(LSB)

TF1	TR1	TF0	TR0	IE1	IT1	IE0	IT0
Timer 1		Timer0		for Interrupt			

TCON Register (2/2)

- **TF** (timer flag, control flag)
 - TF₀ for timer/counter 0; TF₁ for timer/counter 1.
 - TF is like a carry. Originally, TF=0. When TH-TL roll over to 0000 from FFFFH, the TF is set to 1.
 - TF=0 : not reach
 - TF=1: reach
 - If we enable interrupt, TF=1 will trigger ISR.

(MSB)

(LSB)

TF1	TR1	TF0	TR0	IE1	IT1	IE0	IT0
Timer 1		Timer0		for Interrupt			

Equivalent Instructions for the Timer Control Register

For timer 0

SETB TR0	=	SETB TCON.4
-----------------	----------	--------------------

CLR TR0	=	CLR TCON.4
----------------	----------	-------------------

SETB TF0	=	SETB TCON.5
-----------------	----------	--------------------

CLR TF0	=	CLR TCON.5
----------------	----------	-------------------

For timer 1

SETB TR1	=	SETB TCON.6
-----------------	----------	--------------------

CLR TR1	=	CLR TCON.6
----------------	----------	-------------------

SETB TF1	=	SETB TCON.7
-----------------	----------	--------------------

CLR TF1	=	CLR TCON.7
----------------	----------	-------------------

TCON: Timer/Counter Control Register

TF1	TR1	TF0	TR0	IE1	IT1	IE0	IT0
------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------

Timer Mode 1

- In following, we all use timer 0 as an example.
- **16-bit** timer (TH0 and TL0)
- TH0-TL0 is incremented continuously when TR0 is set to 1. And the 8051 stops to increment TH0-TL0 when TR0 is cleared.
- The timer works with the internal system clock. In other words, the timer counts up each machine cycle.
- When the timer (TH0-TL0) reaches its maximum of FFFFH, it rolls over to 0000, and TFO is raised.
- Programmer should check TFO and stop the timer 0.

Steps of Mode 1 (1/3)

1. Choose mode 1 timer 0
 - `MOV TMOD, #01H`
2. Set the original value to TH0 and TLo.
 - `MOV TH0, #FFH`
 - `MOV TLO, #FCH`
3. You had better to clear the flag to monitor: TF0=0.
 - `CLR TF0`
4. Start the timer.
 - `SETB TR0`

Steps of Mode 1 (2/3)

5. The 8051 starts to count up by incrementing the TH0-TL0.
- **TH0-TL0= FFFCH,FFFDH,FFFEH,FFFFH,0000H**

Steps of Mode 1 (3/3)

6. When TH0–TL0 rolls over from FFFFH to 0000, the 8051 set TF0=1.

TH0–TL0= FFFE H, FFFF H, 0000 H (Now TF0=1)

7. Keep monitoring the timer flag (TF) to see if it is raised.

AGAIN: JNB TF0, AGAIN

8. Clear TR0 to stop the process.

CLR TR0

9. Clear the TF flag for the next round.

CLR TF0

Mode 1 Programming

Timer Delay Calculation for XTAL = 11.0592 MHz

(a) in hex

- $(FFFF - YYXX + 1) \times 1.085 \mu s$
- where YYXX are TH, TL initial values respectively.
- Notice that values YYXX are in hex.

(b) in decimal

- Convert YYXX values of the TH, TL register to decimal to get a NNNNN decimal number
- then $(65536 - NNNNN) \times 1.085 \mu s$

Example 9-4 (1/3)

- square wave of 50% duty on P1.5
- Timer 0 is used

;each loop is a half clock

```
MOV TMOD,#01      ;Timer 0,mode 1(16-bit)
HERE: MOV TL0,#0F2H ;Timer value = FFF2H
      MOV TH0,#0FFH
      CPL P1.5
      CLR TF0
      ACALL DELAY
      SJMP HERE
```


Example 9-4 (2/3)

`;generate delay using timer 0`

DELAY:

`SETB TR0` `;start the timer 0`

`AGAIN: JNB TF0, AGAIN`

`CLR TR0` `;stop timer 0`

`CLR TF0` `;clear timer 0 flag`

`RET`

Example 9-4 (3/3)

Solution:

In the above program notice the following steps.

1. TMOD = **0000 0001** is loaded.
2. **FFF2H** is loaded into TH0 – TL0.
3. P1.5 is toggled for the high and low portions of the pulse.
4. The DELAY subroutine using the timer is called.
5. In the DELAY subroutine, timer 0 is started by the “**SETB TR0**” instruction.
6. Timer 0 counts up with the passing of each clock, which is provided by the crystal oscillator.

As the timer counts up, it goes through the states of FFF3, FFF4, FFF5, FFF6, FFF7, FFF8, FFF9, FFFA, FFFB, FFFC, FFFF, FFFE, FFFFH. One more clock rolls it to 0, raising the timer flag (**TF0 = 1**). At that point, the JNB instruction falls through.

7. Timer 0 is stopped by the instruction “**CLR TR0**”. The DELAY subroutine ends, and the process is repeated.

Notice that to repeat the process, we must reload the TL and TH registers, and start the timer again (in the main program).

Example 9-9 (1/2)

- This program generates a square wave on pin P1.5 Using timer 1
- Find the frequency. (don't include the overhead of instruction delay)
- XTAL = 11.0592 MHz

```
        MOV    TMOD, #10H        ;timer 1, mode 1
AGAIN:  MOV    TL1, #34H         ;timer value=3476H
        MOV    TH1, #76H
        SETB  TR1                ;start
BACK:   JNB   TF1, BACK
        CLR   TR1                ;stop
        CPL   P1.5               ;next half clock
        CLR   TF1                ;clear timer flag 1
        SJMP  AGAIN              ;reload timer1
```

Example 9-9 (2/2)

Solution:

$FFFFH - 7634H + 1 = 89CCH = 35276$ clock count

Half period = $35276 \times 1.085 \mu s = 38.274$ ms

Whole period = 2×38.274 ms = 76.548 ms

Frequency = $1 / 76.548$ ms = 13.064 Hz.

Note

Mode 1 is not auto reload then the program must reload the TH1, TL1 register every timer overflow if we want to have a continuous wave.

Find Timer Values

- Assume that XTAL = 11.0592 MHz .
- And we know desired **delay**
- how to find the values for the TH,TL ?
 1. Divide the **delay** by **1.085 μ s** and get **n**.
 2. Perform **65536 -n**
 3. Convert the result of Step 2 to hex (**yyxx**)
 4. Set **TH = yy** and **TL = xx**.

Example 9-12 (1/2)

- Assuming XTAL = 11.0592 MHz,
- write a program to generate a square wave of 50 Hz frequency on pin P2.3.

Solution:

1. The period of the square wave = $1 / 50 \text{ Hz} = 20 \text{ ms}$.
2. The high or low portion of the square wave = 10 ms .
3. $10 \text{ ms} / 1.085 \mu\text{s} = 9216$
4. $65536 - 9216 = 56320$ in decimal = **DC00H** in hex.
5. TL1 = 00H and TH1 = DCH.

Example 9-12 (2/2)

```

        MOV    TMOD,#10H        ;timer 1, mode 1
AGAIN:  MOV    TL1,#00          ;Timer value = DC00H
        MOV    TH1,#0DCH
        SETB   TR1              ;start
BACK:   JNB    TF1,BACK
        CLR    TR1              ;stop
        CPL    P2.3
        CLR    TF1              ;clear timer flag 1
        SJMP   AGAIN            ;reload timer since
                                ;mode 1 is not
                                ;auto-reload
```

Generate a Large Time Delay

- The size of the time delay depends on two factors:
 - The crystal frequency
 - The timer's 16-bit register, TH & TL
- The largest time delay is achieved by making $TH=TL=0$.
- What if that is not enough?
- Next Example show how to achieve large time delay

Example 9-13

Examine the following program and find the time delay in seconds.
Exclude the overhead due to the instructions in the loop.

```
MOV    TMOD , #10H
MOV    R3 , #200
AGAIN: MOV    TL1 , #08
        MOV    TH1 , #01
        SETB   TR1
BACK:   JNB    TF1 , BACK
        CLR    TR1
        CLR    TF1
        DJNZ   R3 , AGAIN
```

Solution:

$TH - TL = 0108H = 264$ in decimal

$65536 - 264 = 65272$.

One of the timer delay = $65272 \times 1.085 \mu s = 70.820$ ms

Total delay = 200×70.820 ms = 14.164024 seconds

Timer Mode 0

- Mode 0 is exactly like mode 1 except that it is a **13-bit** timer instead of 16-bit.
 - 8-bit TH0
 - 5-bit TL0
- The counter can hold values between 0000 to 1FFF in TH0-TL0.
 - $2^{13}-1 = 2000H-1 = 1FFFH$
- We set the initial values TH0-TL0 to **count up**.
- When the timer reaches its maximum of 1FFFH, it rolls over to 0000, and TF0 is raised.

Timer Mode 2

- 8-bit timer.
 - It allows only values of 00 to FFH to be loaded into TH0.
- Auto-reloading
- TLo is incremented continuously when TR0=1.
- next example: 200 MCs delay on timer 0.

Steps of Mode 2 (1/2)

1. Chose mode 2 timer 0

```
MOV TMOD, #02H
```

2. Set the original value to TH0.

```
MOV TH0, #38H
```

3. Clear the flag to TF0=0.

```
CLR TF0
```

4. After TH0 is loaded with the 8-bit value, the 8051 gives a copy of it to TLo.

```
TL0=TH0=38H
```

5. Start the timer.

```
SETB TR0
```

Steps of Mode 2 (2/2)

6. The 8051 starts to count up by incrementing the TLo.
 - `TL0= 38H, 39H, 3AH,`
7. When TLo rolls over from FFH to 00, the 8051 set TF0=1. Also, TLo is reloaded automatically with the value kept by the TH0.
 - `TL0= FEH, FFH, 00H (Now TF0=1)`
 - The 8051 auto reload `TL0=TH0=38H`.
 - `Clr TF0`
 - Go to Step 6 (i.e., TLo is incrementing continuously).
- Note that **we must clear TF0** when TLo rolls over. Thus, we can monitor TF0 in next process.
- Clear TR0 to stop the process.
 - `Clr TR0`

Timer 1 Mode 2 with internal Input

TF goes high when FF \rightarrow 0

Example 9-15

- Find the frequency of a square wave generated on pin P1.0.

Solution:

```
        MOV    TMOD, #2H    ;Timer 0, mode 2
        MOV    TH0, #0
AGAIN:  MOV    R5, #250     ;count 250 times
        ACALL DELAY
        CPL   P1.0
        SJMP  AGAIN
```

```
DELAY:  SETB  TR0          ;start
BACK:   JNB   TF0, BACK    ;wait until TL0 overflow auto-reload
        CLR   TR0          ;stop
        CLR   TF0         ;clear TF
        DJNZ  R5, DELAY
        RET
```

$T = 2 (250 \times 256 \times 1.085 \mu\text{s}) = 138.88 \text{ ms}$, and frequency = 7.2 Hz.

Example 9-16

Assuming that we are programming the timers for mode 2, find the value (in hex) loaded into TH for each of the following cases.

- (a) `MOV TH1, #-200` (b) `MOV TH0, #-60` (c) `MOV TH1, #-3`
(d) `MOV TH1, #-12` (e) `MOV TH0, #-48`

Solution:

Some 8051 assemblers provide this way.

$$-200 = -C8H \Rightarrow 2\text{'s complement of } -200 = 100H - C8H = 38H$$

Decimal	2' s complement (TH value)
-200 = - C8H	38H
- 60 = - 3CH	C4H
- 3	FDH
- 12	F4H
- 48	D0H

Counter

- These timers can also be used as counters **counting events** happening outside the 8051.
- When the timer is used as a counter, it is a pulse outside of the 8051 that increments the TH, TL.
- When **C/T=1**, the counter counts up as pulses are fed from
 - T₀: timer 0 input (Pin 14, P3.4)
 - T₁: timer 1 input (Pin 15, P3.5)

Port 3 Pins Used For Timers 0 and 1

Pin	Port Pin	Function	Description
14	P3.4	T0	Timer/Counter 0 external input
15	P3.5	T1	Timer/Counter 1 external input

(MSB)

(LSB)

GATE	C/T=1	M1	M0	GATE	C/T=1	M1	M0
Timer 1				Timer 0			

Timer/Counter selection

FIGURE 4-5

Timer 1 operating in mode 1

Counter Mode 1

- **16-bit** counter (THo and TLo)
- THo-TLo is incremented when TRo is set to 1 **and** an external pulse (in To) occurs.
- When the counter (THo-TLo) reaches its maximum of FFFFH, it rolls over to 0000, and TFo is raised.
- Programmers should monitor TFo continuously and stop the counter 0.
- Programmers can set the initial value of THo-TLo and let TFo=1 as an indicator to show a special condition. (ex: 100 people have come).

Timer 0 with External Input (Mode 1)

Counter Mode 2

- 8-bit **counter**.
 - It allows only values of 00 to FFH to be loaded into THo.
- Auto-reloading
TLo is incremented if TRo=1 **and** external pulse occurs.

Example 9-18 (1/2)

Assuming that clock pulses are fed into pin T1, write a program for counter 1 in mode 2 to count the pulses and display the state of the TL 1 count on P2.

Solution:

```
        MOV    TMOD, #01100000B    ;mode 2, counter 1
        MOV    TH1, #0
        SETB   P3.5                ;make T1 input port
AGAIN:  SETB   TR1                  ;start
BACK:   MOV    A, TL1
        MOV    P2, A                ;display in P2
        JNB   TF1, Back             ;overflow
        CLR   TR1                  ;stop
        CLR   TF1                  ;make TF=0
        SJMP  AGAIN                ;keep doing it
```

Example 9-18 (2/2)

- Timer 1 as an event counter fed into pin3.5.
- “SETB P3.5” make P3.5 an input port by making it high

P2 is connected to 8 LEDs
and input T1 to pulse.

GATE=1 in TMOD

- All discuss so far has assumed that GATE=0.
 - The timer is started with instructions “**SETB TR0**” and “**SETB TR1**” for timers 0 and 1, respectively.
- If GATE=1, we can use hardware to control the start and stop of the timers.
 - INT0 (P3.2, pin 12) starts and stops timer 0
 - INT1 (P3.3, pin 13) starts and stops timer 1
 - This allows us to start or stop the timer externally at any time via a simple switch.

GATE (external control)

- Timer 0 must be turned on by “**SETB TR0**”
- If GATE=1 count up if
 - INT0 input is high
 - TR0=1
- If GATE=0 count up if
 - TR0=1

Table 4–1

Timer special function registers

TIMER SFR	PURPOSE	ADDRESS	BIT-ADDRESSABLE
TCON	Control	88H	Yes
TMOD	Mode	89H	No
TL0	Timer 0 low-byte	8AH	No
TL1	Timer 1 low-byte	8BH	No
TH0	Timer 0 high-byte	8CH	No
TH1	Timer 1 high-byte	8DH	No
T2CON*	Timer 2 control	C8H	Yes
RCAP2L*	Timer 2 low-byte capture	CAH	No
RCAP2H*	Timer 2 high-byte capture	CBH	No
TL2*	Timer 2 low-byte	CCH	No
TH2*	Timer 2 high-byte	CDH	No

*8032/8052 only

8051 Interrupts

Interrupts Programming

- An *interrupt* is an external or internal event that interrupts the microcontroller to inform it that a device needs its service.

Interrupts vs. Polling

- A single microcontroller can serve **several** devices.
- There are **two** ways to do that:
 - interrupts
 - polling.
- The program which is associated with the interrupt is called the *interrupt service routine* (ISR) or *interrupt handler*.

Steps in executing an interrupt

- Finish current instruction and saves the PC on stack.
- Jumps to a fixed location in memory depend on type of interrupt
- Starts to execute the interrupt service routine until RETI (return from interrupt)
- Upon executing the RETI the microcontroller returns to the place where it was interrupted. Get pop PC from stack

Interrupt Sources

- Original 8051 has 6 sources of interrupts
 - Reset
 - Timer 0 overflow
 - Timer 1 overflow
 - External Interrupt 0
 - External Interrupt 1
 - Serial Port events (buffer full, buffer empty, etc)
- Enhanced version has 22 sources
 - More timers, programmable counter array, ADC, more external interrupts, another serial port (UART)

Interrupt Vectors

Each interrupt has a **specific** place in **code** memory where program execution (interrupt service routine) begins.

External Interrupt 0:	0003h
Timer 0 overflow:	000Bh
External Interrupt 1:	0013h
Timer 1 overflow:	001Bh
Serial :	0023h

Note: that there are only 8 memory locations between vectors.

ISRs and Main Program in 8051

```
SJMP    main
ORG     03H
ljmp    int0sr
ORG     0BH
ljmp    t0sr
ORG     13H
ljmp    int1sr
ORG     1BH
ljmp    t1sr
ORG     23H
ljmp    serialsr
ORG     30H
```

```
main:
```

```
...
```

```
END
```

Interrupt Enable (IE) register

- ❑ All interrupt are disabled after reset
- ❑ We can enable and disable them by IE

D7				D0			
EA	--	ET2	ES	ET1	EX1	ET0	EX0

EA	IE.7	Disables all interrupts.					
--	IE.6	No implemented, reserved for future use					
ET2	IE.5	Enables or disables timer 2 overflow interrupt					
ES	IE.4	Enables or disables the serial port interrupt					
ET1	IE.3	Enables or disables timer 2 overflow interrupt					
EX1	IE.2	Enables or disables external interrupt 1					
ET0	IE.1	Enables or disables timer 0 overflow interrupt					
EX0	IE.0	Enables or disables external interrupt					

Enabling and disabling an interrupt

- ❑ by bit operation
- ❑ Recommended in the middle of program

SETB	EA	SETB	IE.7	; Enable All
SETB	ET0	SETB	IE.1	; Enable Timer0 ovrf
SETB	ET1	SETB	IE.3	; Enable Timer1 ovrf
SETB	EX0	SETB	IE.0	; Enable INT0
SETB	EX1	SETB	IE.2	; Enable INT1
SETB	ES	SETB	IE.4	; Enable Serial port

- ❑ by mov instruction
- ❑ Recommended in the first of program

```
MOV IE, #10010110B
```

Example

- A 10khz square wave with 50% duty cycle (CE)

```
ORG 0 ;Reset entry point
LJMP MAIN ;Jump above interrupt

ORG 000BH ;Timer 0 interrupt vector
T0ISR: CPL P1.0 ;Toggle port bit
      RETI ;Return from ISR to Main program

ORG 0030H ;Main Program entry point
MAIN: MOV TMOD, #02H ;Timer 0, mode 2
      MOV TH0, #0CEH
      MOV IE, #82H
      SETB TR0 ;Start timer

      SJMP $ ;Do nothing just wait
      END
```

Example

- Write a program using interrupts to simultaneously create 7 kHz and 500 Hz square waves on P1.7 and P1.6.

Solution

```
ORG 0
LJMP MAIN
ORG 000BH
LJMP T0ISR
ORG 001BH
LJMP T1ISR
ORG 0030H
MAIN: MOV TMOD, #12H
      MOV TH0, #-71 (B9)
      MOV IE, #8AH
      MOV TH1, #HIGH(-1000) (FC)
      MOV TL1, #LOW(-1000) (18)
      SETB TR0
      SETB TR1
      SJMP $
T0ISR: CPL P1.7
      RETI
T1ISR: CLR TR1
      MOV TH1, #HIGH(-1000) (FC)
      MOV TL1, #LOW(-1000) (18)
      SETB TR1
      CPL P1.6
      RETI
END
```


Timer ISR

- Notice that
 - There is no need for a “CLR TF_x” instruction in timer ISR
 - 8051 clears the TF internally upon jumping to ISR
- Notice that
 - We must reload timer in mode 1
 - There is no need on mode 2 (timer auto reload)

External interrupt type control

- By low nibble of Timer control register **TCON**
- **IE₀** (**IE₁**): External interrupt 0(1) edge flag.
 - **set** by CPU when external interrupt edge (**H-to-L**) is detected.
 - Does not affected by H-to-L while ISR is executed(no int on int)
 - **Cleared** by CPU when **RETI** executed.
 - does **not** latch low-level triggered interrupt
- **IT₀** (**IT₁**): interrupt 0 (1) type control bit.
 - Set/cleared by software
 - IT=1 edge trigger
 - IT=0 low-level trigger

(MSB)

(LSB)

TF1	TR1	TF0	TR0	IE1	IT1	IE0	IT0
Timer 1				Timer0			
for Interrupt							

External Interrupts

Example

- INT1 pin is connected to a switch that is normally high. Whenever it goes low, it should turn on an LED. The LED is connected to P1.1 and is normally off. When it is turned on it should stay ON for a fraction of a second.

Example of external interuupt

```
    ORG 0000H
    LJMP MAIN
;
;interrupt service routine (ISR)
;for hardware external interrupt INT1
;
    ORG 0013H
    SETB P1.1
    MOV R0,200
WAIT: DJNZ R0,WAIT
    CLR P1.1
    RETI
;
;main program for initialization
;
    ORG 30H
MAIN:  SETB IT1           ;on negative edge of INT1
    MOV IE,#10000100B
WAIT2: SJMP WAIT2
    END
```

Example of external interrupt

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 6-5
Furnace example. (a) Hardware connections (b) Timing.

Example of external interuupt

```
Org 0000h
```

```
Ljmp main
```

```
Org 0003h
```

```
x0isr: clr p1.7
```

```
Reti
```

```
Org 0013h
```

```
x1isr: setb p1.7
```

```
Reti
```

```
Org 0030h
```

```
Main: mov IE,#85h
```

```
Setb it0
```

```
Setb it1
```

```
Setb p1.7
```

```
Jb p3.2,skip
```

```
Clr p1.7
```

```
Skip: Sjmp $
```

```
end
```

Interrupt Priorities

- What if **two** interrupt sources interrupt at the **same time**?
- The interrupt with the **highest** PRIORITY gets serviced **first**.
- All interrupts have a power on **default** priority order.
 1. External interrupt 0 (INT0)
 2. Timer interrupt0 (TF0)
 3. External interrupt 1 (INT1)
 4. Timer interrupt1 (TF1)
 5. Serial communication (RI+TI)
- Priority can also be set to “high” or “low” by **IP** reg.

Interrupt Priorities (IP) Register

IP.7: reserved

IP.6: reserved

IP.5: timer 2 interrupt priority bit(8052 only)

IP.4: serial port interrupt priority bit

IP.3: timer 1 interrupt priority bit

IP.2: external interrupt 1 priority bit

IP.1: timer 0 interrupt priority bit

IP.0: external interrupt 0 priority bit

Interrupt Priorities Example

- **MOV IP , #00000100B** or **SETB IP.2** gives priority order
 1. Int1
 2. Int0
 3. Timer0
 4. Timer1
 5. Serial
- **MOV IP , #00001100B** gives priority order
 1. Int1
 2. Timer1
 3. Int0
 4. Timer0
 5. Serial

Interrupt inside an interrupt

- ❑ A high-priority interrupt **can** interrupt a low-priority interrupt
- ❑ All interrupt are latched internally
- ❑ Low-priority interrupt wait until 8051 has finished servicing the high-priority interrupt

Serial Communication

Basics of serial communication

- Parallel: expensive - short distance - fast
- Serial :cheaper- long (two different cities by modem)-slow

Figure 10-1. Serial versus Parallel Data Transfer

Basics of serial communication

Figure 10-2. Simplex, Half-, and Full-Duplex Transfers

Start and stop bits

- When there is **no** transfer the signal is **high**
Transmission begins with a start (**low**) bit
LSB first Finally 1 stop bit (**high**)
Data transfer rate (baud rate) is stated in **bps**
bps: bit per second

Figure 10-3. Framing ASCII "A" (41H)

How to communicate 8051 to PC

- ❑ Connect TXD to RXD and RXD to TXD from pc to 8051
- ❑ The baud rate of the 8051 must matched the baud rate of the pc
- ❑ PC standard baud rate
 - ❖ 2400-4800-9600-14400-19200-28800-33600-57600
- ❑ Serial mode 1 is used
- ❑ Timer 1 is used
- ❑ The 8051 UART divides the **machine cycle** frequency by 32
- ❑ Machine cycle is $\frac{1}{12}$ XTAL frequency
- ❑ We use timer1 in mode 2 (auto reload)
- ❑ See example 10-1

RxD and TxD pins in the 8051

- TxD pin 11 of the 8051 (P3.1)
- RxD pin 10 of the 8051 (P3.0)

SBUF register

```
MOV    SBUF, #'D'    ;load SBUF=44H, ASCII for 'D'  
MOV    SBUF, A       ;copy accumulator into SBUF  
MOV    A, SBUF       ;copy SBUF into accumulator
```

Serial port block diagram

FIGURE 5-1
Serial port block diagram

Example 10-1

With XTAL = 11.0592 MHz, find the TH1 value needed to have the following baud rates. (a) 9600 (b) 2400 (c) 1200

Solution:

With XTAL = 11.0592 MHz, we have:

The machine cycle frequency of the 8051 = $11.0592 \text{ MHz} / 12 = 921.6 \text{ kHz}$, and $921.6 \text{ kHz} / 32 = 28,800 \text{ Hz}$ is the frequency provided by UART to timer 1 to set baud rate.

(a) $28,800 / 3 = 9600$

where $-3 = \text{FD (hex)}$ is loaded into TH1

(b) $28,800 / 12 = 2400$

where $-12 = \text{F4 (hex)}$ is loaded into TH1

(c) $28,800 / 24 = 1200$

where $-24 = \text{E8 (hex)}$ is loaded into TH1

Notice that dividing 1/12th of the crystal frequency by 32 is the default value upon activation of the 8051 RESET pin. We can change this default setting. This is explained at the end of this chapter.

Table 10-4: Timer 1 TH1 Register Values for Various Baud Rates

Baud Rate	TH1 (Decimal)	TH1 (Hex)
9600	-3	FD
4800	-6	FA
2400	-12	F4
1200	-24	E8

Note: XTAL = 11.0592 MHz.

Serial control (SCON) Register

SM0 (SCON.7) : mode specifier

SM1 (SCON.6) : mode specifier

SM2 (SCON.5) : used for multi processor communication

REN (SCON.4) : receive enable (by software enable/disable)

TB8 (SCON.3) : transmit bit8

RB8 (SCON.2) : receive bit 8

TI (SCON.1) : transmit interrupt flag set by HW clear by SW

RI (SCON.0) : receive interrupt flag set by HW clear by SW

Mode of operation

SM0	SM1	MODE	operation	transmit rate
0	0	0	shift register	fixed (xtal/12)
0	1	1	8 bit UART	variable (timer1)
1	0	2	9 bit UART	fixed (xtal/32 or xtal/64)
1	1	3	9 bit UART	variable (timer1)

Mode of operation

- Mode 0 :
 - Serial **data** enters and exits through **RxD**
 - **TxD** outputs the shift **clock**.
 - 8 bits are transmitted/received(LSB first)
 - The baud rate is fixed a $1/12$ the oscillator frequency.

Mode of operation

- Mode 1
 - Ten bits are transmitted (through TxD) or received (through RxD)
 - A start bit (0), 8 data bits (LSB first), and a stop bit (1)
 - On receive, the stop bit goes into RB8 in SCON
 - the baud rate is determined by the Timer 1 overflow rate.
 - Timer1 clock is $1/32$ or $1/16$ of machine cycle (MC= $1/12$ XTAL)
 - Transmission is initiated by any instruction that uses SBUF as a destination register.
 - $1/\text{BAUD RATE} = [((\text{FF}-\text{TH1})+1) \times 12 \times 32] / \text{Fosc} \times 2^{\text{smod}}$
 - Baud Rate = $[2^{\text{smod}} / 32] \times [\text{Timer 1 overflow rate}]$

Mode of operation

(a) Mode 0

(b) Mode 2

(c) Modes 1 and 3

Mode of operation

- Mode 2 :
 - **Eleven** bits are transmitted (through TxD), received (through RxD)
 - A start bit (0)
 - 8 data bits (LSB first)
 - A programmable 9th data bit
 - and a stop bit (1)
 - On transmit, the 9th bit (**TB8**) can be assigned 0 or 1.
 - On receive, the 9th data bit goes into **RB8** in SCON.
 - the 9th can be **parity** bit
 - The baud rate is programmable to 1/32 or 1/64 the oscillator frequency in Mode 2 by **SMOD** bit in **PCON** register
 - Baud Rate = $[2^{\text{smod}} / 64] \times [F_{\text{osc}}/12]$
- Mode 3
 - Same as mode 2
 - But may have a **variable** baud rate generated from Timer 1.

What is SMOD

- ❑ Bit 7 of PCON register
- ❑ If SMOD=1 **double** baud rate
- ❑ PCON is not bit addressable
- ❑ How to set SMOD

```
Mov a, pcon
```

```
Setb acc.7
```

```
Mov pcon, a
```


Serial example(1)

An example of sending a message.

```
;initialization
    MOV TMOD,#20H
    MOV TH1,#-12
    MOV SCON,#50H
;begin to transmit
    SETB TR1
AGAIN1: MOV A,#'B'
        CALL TRANSS
        MOV A,#'A'
        CALL TRANSS
        MOV A,#'L'
        CALL TRANSS
        MOV A,#'L'
        CALL TRANSS
        SJMP AGAIN1
;seial transmitting subroutine
TRANSS: MOV SBUF,A
AGAIN2: JNB TI,AGAIN2
        CLR TI
        RET
        END
```

Serial example(2)

An example for serial port interrupt

```

    ORG 0000H
    LJMP MAIN
;jump to serial ISR
    ORG 23H
    LJMP ISR
;main program
    ORG 30H
;1-initialization
MAIN:  MOV P0,#0FFH
        MOV TMOD,#20H
        MOV TH1,#-12
        MOV SCON,#50H
        MOV IE,#90H
;2-begin
        SETB TR1
AGAIN: MOV A,P0
        MOV SBUF,A
        MOV P1,A
        SJMP AGAIN
;
;ISR for reading from serial port
ISR:  PUSH ACC
        JB TI,TRANSM
        MOV A,SBUF
        MOV P2,A
        CLR RI
        SJMP ISREND
TRANSM: CLR TI
ISREND: POP ACC
        RETI
        END
```

Serial example(3)

an example for serial port
interrupt

 ;for transmitting

ORG 0000H

LJMP MAIN

;jump to serial ISR

ORG 23H

LJMP ISR

;main program

ORG 30H

;initialization

```
MAIN:  MOV P0,#0FFH
        MOV TMOD,#20H
        MOV TH1,#-13
        MOV SCON,#50H
        MOV IE,#90H
```

;2-begin

SETB TR1

```
AGAIN: SJMP AGAIN
```

;ISR for receive from serial to p0
;transmitting to serial from p1

```
ISR:   JB TI,TRANSM
        MOV A,SBUF
        mov P0,A
        CLR RI
        RETI
```

```
TRANSM: MOV A,P1
          MOV SBUF,A
          CLR TI
          RETI
          END
```

Power control register

BIT	SYMBOL	FUNCTION
PCON.7	SMOD	Double Baud rate bit. When set to a 1 and Timer 1 is used to generate baud rate, and the Serial Port is used in modes 1, 2, or 3.
PCON.6	—	Reserved.
PCON.5	—	Reserved.
PCON.4	—	Reserved.
PCON.3	GF1	General-purpose flag bit.
PCON.2	GF0	General-purpose flag bit.
PCON.1	PD	Power-Down bit. Setting this bit activates power-down operation.
PCON.0	IDL	Idle mode bit. Setting this bit activate idle mode operation.

Power control

- A standard for applications where power consumption is critical
- two power reducing modes
 - Idle
 - Power down

Idle mode

- An instruction that sets PCON.0 causes Idle mode
 - Last instruction executed before going into the Idle mode
 - the internal CPU clock is gated off
 - Interrupt, Timer, and Serial Port functions act normally.
 - All of registers, ports and internal RAM maintain their data during Idle
 - ALE and PSEN hold at logic high levels
- Any interrupt
 - will cause PCON.0 to be cleared by HW (terminate Idle mode)
 - then execute ISR
 - with RETI return and execute next instruction after Idle instruction.
- RST signal clears the IDL bit directly

Power-Down Mode

- An instruction that sets PCON.1 causes power down mode
- Last instruction executed before going into the power down mode
- the on-chip oscillator is stopped.
- all functions are stopped, the contents of the on-chip RAM and Special Function Registers are maintained.
- The ALE and PSEN output are held low
- The **reset** that terminates Power Down

Power control example

```
Org 0000h
```

```
Ljmp main
```

```
Org 0003h
```

```
Orl pcon,#02h      ;power down mode
```

```
Reti
```

```
Org 0030h
```

Main:

```
.....
```

```
.....
```

```
.....
```

```
Orl pcon,#01h      ;Idle mode
```

```
end
```

Interrupts

```
...  
mov a, #2  
mov b, #16  
mul ab  
mov R0, a  
mov R1, b  
mov a, #12  
mov b, #20  
mul ab  
add a, R0  
mov R0, a  
mov a, R1  
addc a, b  
mov R1, a  
end
```

Program Execution

interrupt


```
ISR: inc r7  
     mov a, r7  
     jnz NEXT  
     cpl P1.6
```

NEXT: **reti**

return

PORT Structure

8051 Programming Examples

Example

Write a program using interrupts to do the following:

- Receive data serially and send it to p0.
- Read port p1 and transmit serially and a copy given to p2.
- Make timero generate a square wave of 5 KHz frequency on p0.1.

Assume that XTAL=11.0592MHZ. Set the baud rate at 4800.

Example

- Assume 10 bytes of data are stored from RAM location 50H. Compute the average of these numbers and store the result at memory location 40H.
- For the code fragment, compute the size and the time needed assuming 11.0582MHz crystal

Example

- Assume 10 bytes of data are stored from location 3000H in the external memory. Sort them in ascending order.